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Returning to Anjiang Village: the Intellectual Legacy and Art Education Philosophy of National Academy of Art

Yao Feng

Abstract

In 1939, the National Academy of Art, formed by the merger of the Beiping Art School and the Hangzhou Art School, moved west to Anjiang Village, marking a brief yet crucial period in its educational history. Many teachers and students actively joined the cultural and artistic front, working together to overcome challenges. Despite the difficult conditions, the National Academy of Art faculty and students did not forget to spread the seeds of culture, using education and culture to rescue the nation in times of peril. They created numerous outstanding works of art, nurtured many exceptional artists, and wrote a brilliant chapter in the history of modern Chinese art. Simultaneously, they also prepared a large pool of talent for developing literature and art, culture, education, artistic education, and propaganda in New China, exerting a profound influence on our country's art education field.

Key Words

Anjiang Village, National Academy of Art, resistance and nation-saving, intellectual legacy, art education

In 1937, the full-scale outbreak of the Second Sino-Japanese War brought unprecedented devastation to China's higher education system. Many higher education institutions were forced to relocate to continue the cultural and educational legacy. Amid the turmoil of war, the National Academy of Art, formed by the merger of the Beiping and Hangzhou art schools, underwent several relocations before settling in Kunming, Yunnan.

In June 1938, the Ministry of Education appointed Teng Gu as the school's president. Amid the ongoing war, he oversaw the merger and reorganization of the National Academy of Art. He led the faculty and students from Hunan's Yuanling on a journey to Kunming, passing through Guiyang. They eventually settled in the village of Anjiang on the outskirts of Kunming, enduring many hardships and challenges during these turbulent times.

Throughout this process, they firmly believed in the victory of the anti-Japanese resistance. They had a deep sense of patriotism, connecting the fate of their homeland with their destiny. With a solid commitment to art, they courageously and confidently advanced on the path of serving their country through art. While dedicating them-

selves to their studies and passing on their knowledge, they also used various art forms such as paintings, sculpture, theater, and songs as weapons to engage in propaganda and mobilize the people against the enemy. They became a unique force during the war, exemplifying the spirit of excellent resistance and contributing to a magnificent chapter in the history of China's wartime efforts.

As the only national higher education institution specialized in the arts, the National Academy of Art was responsible for preserving and continuing the tradition of art education in China. They did not disappoint in this mission. They gathered a team of top art educators in China and went beyond pure art to cultivate numerous art talents with a deep love for their country and a strong spirit of creativity. They supplied many art warriors during wartime and created numerous artworks related to the resistance. Moreover, they cultivated a talent for developing the arts in New China and promoted the contemporary development of Chinese art education. The National Academy of Art became an essential model in the history of higher art education in China and created a

vivid chapter in Chinese art education history. The spirit of resistance and the artistic legacy of the National Academy of Art will forever be recorded in history.

1. Artistic Activities during the War of Resistance

As the War of Resistance approached and the nation faced a critical juncture, the ideological belief in the art that took precedence was replaced by the enthusiasm for the cause of resisting Japanese aggression and saving the nation. With the progression of the times, the original “School Song of Hangzhou Art College” proclaimed “Art school youths, vigorously wield your brushes! Art school youths, vigorously strike your chisels! Let’s rebuild the art world in Asia! Let art shine everywhere!”¹ was transformed, with lyrics composed by the school’s president Teng Gu, into the “National Academy of Art Anthem”, which began, “Majestic is the land of China, a great civilization spanning five thousand years, shining like a timeless star. Grand creations and beautiful landscapes fill our generation with brilliance. With fervent blood, we adorn our land, preventing it from being trampled. We sing passionately for our nation, ensuring it is not subjected to oppression. We build sturdy fortresses to defend our territory and people. We carve dignified sculptures, immortalizing the names of heroes for all time. To create the history of humanity, we offer our entire lives.”² The new school song was infused with the heroic spirit of sacrificing for the nation’s survival.

During this period, they ventured beyond the ivory tower of art and began to experience the practical realities and atmosphere of the real world. “The storm of life eventually came crashing down on the faculty, and students were expelled from paradise. They plunged into the hardships of the masses and tasted the bitterness of displacement. They discovered that within the ‘stench’ and ‘ugliness’ of the laborers lay true beauty. They started sketching scenes from life, capturing life through art. The rich vitality of life enveloped us, inspiring a new aesthetic perspective.” The educational philosophy of the National Academy of Art in Anjiang Village shifted from “art for the sake of art” to “art reflecting life, art in service of the war.” Faculty and students actively engaged in propaganda activities for the resistance, wielding art as a weapon. At the intersection of history, they steered the turbulent wave of art away from falling, supported the edifice of education and prevented it from collapsing, continued the grand legacy of their predecessors, and contributed to the nation’s construction.

The National Academy of Art created many resistance and nation-saving artworks during this period. It cultivated numerous outstanding talents to develop the

arts in New China. Therefore, it is also known as the Southwest United University of the Arts. Today, the Central Conservatory of Music, the Central Academy of Fine Arts, the China Academy of Art, and the Academy of Arts and Design at Tsinghua University all consider Anjiang Village as the place to trace their school’s roots and history, viewing the Anjiang Village period as a formative period for their school’s spirit.

After the National Academy of Art relocated to Kunhua Elementary School, in addition to their regular academic activities, they continued to harness the power of art and actively engaged in various forms of anti-Japanese propaganda activities. To teach literacy to the local population, the students established the Anjiang Night School, offering free evening classes that were well-received by the villagers. Apart from their studies, they also had extracurricular activities, such as performing in rural areas to promote resistance efforts and going on outings to understand the local situation and become familiar with Kunming. This made school life consistently vivid and dynamic.

During their study life in Anjiang Village, their artworks underwent a significant transformation, becoming more expansive and fresh or rugged and simple, replacing the exoticism that had permeated the cramped art studios and bustling salons before the war. What was ignited within them was the passion for resisting Japanese aggression and saving the nation, expressing the emotional ambitions of the faculty and students to contribute their art to the cause of the war and the nation’s survival at a critical juncture. In the early stages of the resistance, especially during their exile, the faculty and students picked up their brushes to create propaganda art for the war, craft slogans, and participate in various forms of resistance and nation-saving activities. They organized exhibitions to support the cause.

During the Anjiang Village period, the National Academy of Art organized several art exhibitions as part of their artistic activities during the War of Resistance. On March 20, 1939, the National Academy of Art held its first exhibition in Kunming, which took place at the Kunming Civil Education Hall (Kunming Confucius Temple) and the Zhi Gong Hall of Yunnan University. This exhibition showcased sketches and watercolor paintings the faculty and students created during their journey from Yuanling, Hunan to Kunming, depicting the landscapes and scenes they encountered along the way, including challenging mountainous terrain and minority regions. The exhibition garnered significant attention and excitement among the citizens of Kunming. At the same time, a group of students interested in woodcut comics

and more than twenty others, including art editors from *Yunnan Daily*, collaborated to establish the Kunming Branch Preparatory Committee of the Chinese Woodcut Art for Resistance Association. They actively engaged in activities and created and published a series of woodcut comic works in newspapers and magazines such as *Yi Shi Bao*, *Yunnan Daily*, and *Republic Daily*.

On July 7, 1939, the Student Self-Government Association of the National Academy of Art's Propaganda Division organized its second art exhibition in Kunming at the Zhi Gong Hall of Yunnan University. This exhibition primarily featured woodcut comics related to the War of Resistance. Additionally, it included oil paintings and traditional Chinese paintings used as propaganda art for the resistance, such as Chinese landscape paintings turned into sequential art for anti-Japanese purposes. After the exhibition, the proceeds from the sale of art catalogs and the exhibition were entirely donated to support the frontlines of the war.

On September 30, 1939, while the National Academy of Art held its graduation ceremony at Kunhua Elementary School, a three-day graduation art exhibition co-occurred. The displayed works included Chinese painting, watercolor, oil painting, charcoal drawing, patterns, sculpture, and more, organized in seven exhibition rooms. This marked the third art exhibition the National Academy of Art in Kunming held.

From October 1 to October 5, 1939, the National Academy of Art held its fourth art exhibition at the Cuihu Hotel. This exhibition featured the calligraphy and painting works of the school's faculty member, Chang Shuhong.

The National Academy of Art held its fifth art exhibition in Kunming from November 12 to 16, 1939, at the Christian Youth Association at No. 4 Dingxin Street. This exhibition was organized by the National Academy of Art's student group, the David Art Society, as a fundraiser for winter clothing for frontline soldiers. The exhibited works included over two hundred pieces of art, encompassing oil paintings, traditional Chinese paintings, patterns, compositions related to the War of Resistance, watercolor paintings, sketches, and more. Many pieces were ordered for purchase. These exhibitions, despite their diverse content and styles, collectively represented the educational level and artistic pursuits of the National Academy of Art. They showcased the school's unwavering commitment to education during the war and its practical support for the resistance. Additionally, the school's diverse artistic expressions and techniques, along with its fusion of Eastern and Western ideologies to some extent, contri-

Figure 1. In 1939, a street woodcut exhibition was held in Kunming.

buted to the development of the art movement in Yunnan. In the same year, the school also collected over 400 pieces of artwork from Chinese and Western painting groups to participate in a Soviet art exhibition.

Furthermore, there were various street propaganda activities. The National Academy of Art formed an anti-Japanese propaganda team during their relocation, conducting anti-Japanese song and drama performances and anti-Japanese painting propaganda along the way. After arriving in Kunming, the National Academy of Art's anti-Japanese propaganda team actively organized activities and engaged in anti-Japanese propaganda on the streets and in the fields of Kunming. In 1939, the National Academy of Art conducted anti-Japanese propaganda on August 13th and September 18th memorial days in places such as Guandu, Longtou Village, and the city center of Kunming near the Jinri Building. The propaganda team was divided into drama, singing, wall posters, comics, and condolence groups to carry out their activities. Students from the painting group exhibited propaganda paintings in the streets and squares, explaining their significance to the public. The drama and singing group performed "Put Down Your Whip" and anti-Japanese and nation-saving songs on the

streets. The public gathered from all directions to watch the performances, listen to the songs, and hear the speeches, creating a vibrant atmosphere.

During this period, the National Academy of Art initiated a woodcut movement. To commemorate the September 18th Incident, students from the school created woodcut cards. In the name of the Woodcut Association's Yunnan Branch, they organized four teams to sell these woodcut cards along the streets. The proceeds from these sales were all contributed to the Yunnan Provincial Anti-Japanese Support Association. A street woodcut exhibition was also held near the Jinri Building in the city center. The students' comic woodcut works from the National Academy of Art significantly enriched the layout of various newspapers and magazines in Yunnan. Their illustrated comic woodcuts added an element of fun to the reading experience and enhanced the effectiveness of the newspapers' propaganda efforts for the War of Resistance.

After the Second Sino-Japanese War outbreak, artists wielded their paintings as weapons and engaged in propaganda activities for the resistance. Artists with various artistic perspectives found common ground in their thoughts and emotions through their efforts in the national cause. The tumultuous and challenging life experiences allowed them to empathize with the joys and sorrows of ordinary people. Many scholars and artists living in coastal cities in southeastern China moved to the interior, and the arduous journeys and the open vistas of the natural landscapes changed their way of life and, more importantly, transformed their spiritual beliefs. This led to new emotional shades in the art of Chinese painters and contributed to a renewed artistic thrust, accumulating strength for a new era of art.³

2. Status of Faculty and Students

In the 1930s, as the nationwide situation deteriorated during the Second Sino-Japanese War, numerous colleges and research institutions relocated to the South and West. Amid the tumultuous and challenging war years, the National Academy of Art persevered in its commitment to education. During their westward journey, the faculty and students of the National Academy of Art witnessed the hardships endured by the people and the devastation of the land. Still, they also experienced the grandeur of the landscape and the people's resilience. Today, as they return to Anjiang Village, the land that bears the imprints of their youthful years and struggles, the traces of that eventful period remain discernible.

The National Academy of Art faculty and students who moved to Anjiang Village attended classes, sketched,

and painted at the Jade Emperor Temple and Earth Store Bodhisattva Temple. During their holidays, they would gather by the shores of Dianchi Lake for outdoor sketching and leisurely outings, enjoying happy and blissful moments amidst the lush surroundings of Dianchi Lake during spring and summer. This was a remarkable stroke of fortune in an era marked by the turmoil of war and the smoke of battle. Renowned painter Wu Guanzhong, who graduated from the National Academy of Art, reminisced about his student days in Anjiang Village, saying, "This period was significant and critical. The presence of great masters allowed young students to wholeheartedly focus on learning, nurturing a new generation of masters and outstanding artists for the future of Chinese painting."⁴ Returning to Anjiang Village once more to relive the memories of the National Academy of Art, he expressed his sentiments, noting that Anjiang Village still holds his youth and his dreams. Many of those youthful students from back then have dispersed across the country, and some of them are no longer with us. He wrote, "Rare are the visits from old friends, recalling our youth, scattered far and wide."⁵

In June 1938, Teng Gu, appointed by the Ministry of Education, assumed the position of President of the National Academy of Art. His educational philosophy was to "build a foundation on solid and profound cultural attainments, follow the path of loftiness and greatness, and aim to achieve creativity in the new era." Regarding artistic creativity, he advocated "avoiding superficiality, novelty, bias, and deformity." In the context of the nationwide resistance against the Japanese invasion, President Teng Gu guided both teachers and students to step out of the ivory tower of art, understand the aspirations of the nation and the people, and engage in anti-enemy propaganda work. This demonstrated his distinct stance. He strengthened theatrical propaganda, promoted woodcut art, and encouraged teachers and students to experience the "Long March in the Interior." This phrase symbolized the migration of higher education institutions to the rural areas during wartime. During a national crisis and constant turmoil, the President personally experienced the relocation of the National Academy of Art, exerting great efforts to preserve the school's intellectual heritage and artistic spirit.

"Our school was established in the autumn when the Second Sino-Japanese War began. The survival and death of our nation are closely linked to it. When the nation faces adversity, every individual has a responsibility. We must deeply understand and adhere to the profound teachings of Zeng Zi and follow the clear example of Premier (Chiang Kai-shek) to make great contributions to our lives and serve our country. We should be diligent

and hardworking, endure hardships, remain modest when prosperous, and be resolute in adversity. We should serve our country with unwavering determination, knowing that the country's well-being is more important than our interests. By saving the nation from danger and rejuvenating the people, if everyone can bear heavy responsibilities and strive for excellence, we will ensure victory in the resistance against the enemy and the establishment of a new nation, and humanity worldwide will share in the blessings. The fulfillment of one's aspirations is here, and the purpose of serving the country is also here. Fellow students, be inspired."⁶ President Teng Gu took on this responsibility during a crisis and devoted great care and effort to establishing and managing the nation's only National Academy of Art.

On June 25, during a tea gathering with the graduates, Teng Gu stated, "Why have we come here? Why did the entire school's faculty and students embark on this journey to the countryside? This painful experience is etched in the hearts of everyone, and it will never be erased. Every time we gather, it is a new moment for reflection. Anyone with a trace of vitality naturally feels the need to uplift themselves from this environment and create a bright future. So, we know we are not here to lead a reclusive life in the mountains and forests, and this place is not a utopia."

"Our sacred resistance against Japan has reached its highest stage and is on the verge of victory. The international situation is getting more tense. We should feel the weight of our responsibility and strengthen our confidence in victory." He earnestly encouraged this group of "warriors for the national rejuvenation who are heading to the front lines" to advance resolutely, develop their artistic personalities, be steadfast and vigorous, manifest the virtues of the Chinese nation, become outstanding individuals, and produce top-tier works.

On July 1, 1940, at the beginning of the new academic year, Teng Gu wrote a letter to all the teaching staff, expressing his desire to work with everyone to support art education, impart knowledge, and cultivate talent for the nation. He emphasized the need to raise the academic standards, establish a rigorous teaching approach, enhance students' academic performance, instill central values, and nurture well-rounded individuals who can contribute to the country. He concluded with a deep hope that everyone would recognize the importance of national art education, maintain a sense of loyalty and broad-mindedness, bear the heavy responsibility, and work together to achieve their goals. Teng Gu had great confidence and expectations for conducting education in Anjiang Village.

Although the National Academy of Art's time in Anjiang Village was not long, it was a significant and pivotal period in the academy's history during the Second Sino-Japanese War. This period saw the academy offering the most diverse range of programs and having the most significant number of students, making it a profoundly meaningful and crucial time. Anjiang Village also left deep impressions on both teachers and students.

Despite the hardships and numerous leadership changes, the intellectual legacy of the National Academy of Art remained unbroken, and its academic atmosphere persisted. While the wave of famous art movements surged, most faculty and students maintained a strong interest in Western modern art, directing more of their passion towards modernist painting in their teaching. Realistic styles did not capture their interest. In 1938, Lin Fengmian wrote the phrase "For the Sake of Art" to his students, attempting to merge the formal elements of Western Cubism with the brushwork and spiritual essence of traditional Chinese painting to create an ideal Chinese painting style with a modern touch. However, given the specific societal conditions at the time, this artistic ideal was not aligned with societal needs. Consequently, during the later period in the rear areas, they gradually found themselves in a culturally marginal position. This contrasted with the mainstream and marginal status in Central University, represented by Xu Beihong. Lin Fengmian once told the school's faculty and students, "Those who consider themselves pure artists should realize that art is inseparable from the background of the times. If the background of the times is too distant, the content of art will inevitably be empty, and artworks with shallow content cannot withstand the test of time."⁷ However, it cannot be denied that Lin Fengmian's quiet exploration of ink painting with the fusion of Chinese and Western art during this period was precious and enlightening. It was a precious cultural heritage and a valuable experience for his artistic journey and, indeed, for the path of fusion in Chinese painting throughout the twentieth century.

According to the payroll record, in December 1939, the academy had forty-four staff members. Due to the relocation to a rural area far from the city, the school added three administrative staff members and hired three new faculty members, Li Ruinian, Xiao Chuanjiu, and Li Jianchen. This brought the total number of teaching and administrative staff to fifty-one. Among them, aside from the school principal Teng Gu and academic director Fang Ganmin, the faculty included Pan Tianshou, Wu Fuzhi, and Zhang Zhenduo as instructors in traditional Chinese painting; Chang Shuhong, Qin Xuanfu, Guan Liang, Li Ruinian, Cai Renda, Zhao Renlin, and Li Jian-

Figure 2. In 1939, Zhao Wuji and his classmates took a group photo in front of the classroom of Anjiang Village National Academy of Art in Kunming, Yunnan (Zhao Wuji is the second from the left in the front row). It was collected by the Art Museum of the China Academy of Fine Arts and donated by Xu Tiesheng's family.

chen as instructors in Western painting; Wang Linyi, Xiao Chuanjiu, and Chen Zhixiu as sculpture instructors; Xia Changshi, Yin Beijiu, Tang Jun, and Chai Fei as instructors in the field of design; and Tang Xueyong and Huang Youkui as music instructors. Xu Fancheng was the instructor for art history, Bao Qianyuan taught French, and Gu Liang served as the library director.

The National Academy of Art's faculty, while not large in number, formed a powerful team. In terms of their educational background, out of the twenty-two faculty members (except for some whose backgrounds are unclear, including those in the traditional Chinese painting group such as Pan Tianshou, Wu Fuzhi, Zhang Zhenduo, and Chai Fei, who graduated from Zhejiang Provincial First Normal School and Shanghai Art Academy, and Bao Qianyuan, who graduated from Peking University's Department of Foreign Languages) the other fourteen instructors had studied abroad at renowned art institutions. Among them, Chang Shuhong, Wang Linyi, Li Ruinian, Qin Xuanfu, Tang Jun, Yin Beijiu, and Chen Xiuzhi graduated from the *École des Beaux-Arts* in Paris, France, Guan Liang graduated from the Tokyo Pacific Art Academy in Japan, Xiao Chuanjiu

graduated from the Tokyo Art Department of the University of Japan, Li Jianchen graduated from the University of London in the United Kingdom, Xu Fancheng graduated from Heidelberg University in Germany, Xia Changshi graduated from Tübingen University in Germany, Tang Xueyong graduated from the Lyon National Music Academy in France, and Huang Youkui graduated from Huntington University in the United States. Moreover, when these instructors were in Anjiang Village, they were mainly between the ages of thirty and forty, having engaged in creative activities and taught at higher art institutions for many years. They had extensive experience and profound knowledge and enjoyed great reputations. Additionally, each professor had their unique artistic style and approach. As a result, the school naturally had a diverse and inclusive environment with various artistic styles and schools of thought.

According to the Yunnan Provincial Archives' "Post-war relocation of Yunnan's specialized schools and above questionnaire", during the Anjiang Village period, the National Academy of Art had 255 students. Due to the nature of art education, both the former Beiping Art

School and Hangzhou Art School, which merged to form the National Academy of Art, had high school departments for admitting junior high school graduates. After the merger, the high vocational department for junior high school graduates continued. In the 1939 academic year, it was changed to a five-year specialized program for junior high school students. As a result, the National Academy of Art students' age structure differed from other higher education institutions, with approximately half of them being young students aged fifteen to eighteen. At the same time, the rest fell between the ages of nineteen and twenty-five.

At the same time, this remained true because the National Academy of Art admitted students from all over the country, even after relocating to Kunming during wartime. According to the *Retrospective of the National Academy of Art* compiled by the National Academy of Art Alumni Association and information from the Zhejiang Provincial Archives, a list of 252 students who attended the school during the Kunming period has been compiled. Among these names, I have observed individuals who later became renowned artists or prominent figures in art education. These individuals hailed from various parts of China and worldwide, achieving remarkable success in art. In chronological order of their enrollment, some of these notable figures include:

Chinese-French painter Zhao Wuji
 Painter and author of *Founding of the Nation* Dong Xiwen
 Landscape painter of the Snow Mountain School Li Chenlan
 Painter and Professor Gao Guanhua
 Art educator and Dunhuang scholar Li Yu
 The first ethnic Chinese academician of the French Academy, Zhu Dequn
 Sculpture master Zhu Peijun
 Painter Li Jike
 Pioneer of modern painting in Chaozhou and Shantou, Wu Cangshi
 Oil painter Ding Tianque
 Musician Mo Guixin
 Artist Min Xiwen
 Renowned oil painter Liu Yiwen
 Painter and Professor Li Yifu
 Painter and Professor Zhu Ying
 Art educationist Tu Shixiang
 Painter Wu Guanzhong
 Painter Pu Wenzhi
 Soprano singer Zhang Quan
 Craftsman Huang Jiling
 Painter Lu Shanqun

Art educationist Min Shuqian
 Painter, Professor Yang Yunlong
 Musician Shi Zhenghao
 Art historian Ruan Pu
 Painter and Professor Cheng Baizhou
 One of the founders of the discipline of arts and crafts, Wu Mifeng
 Craftsman Zhou Shaomiao
 Painter and Professor Liu Fuhui
 Painter Fu Benxian
 Craftsman Hao Shilin
 Art theorist and archaeologist Liu Dunyuan
 Leftist artist Huang Rongcan
 Sculptor Li Xuanjian
 Female sculptor Chen Heyi
 Renowned Dunhuang scholar Duan Wenjie and others.

In a relatively small institution, the high proportion of distinguished teachers and the multitude of outstanding alums are truly commendable. The National Academy of Art's journey to Anjiang Village brought a profound sense of national spirit and school atmosphere wherever it went. World-renowned scholars or famous artists taught the young students immersed in this environment. The National Academy of Art was not just a place where art giants taught. It was also the birthplace of contemporary painting masters. Xu Jiang, the president of the China Academy of Art, commented on this westward migration history during the school's ninetieth-anniversary celebration, saying, "Above the mountains, rivers, and lakes, they sought ancient homes and set up drawing tables, gathered renowned teachers and established lofty standards. In the most challenging times, they still upheld their ideals." "The persistence of ideals transformed the land scorched by the fires of war into an endless classroom for those wandering and allowed China, amid peril, to maintain the heart of heaven and earth, giving birth to new life for its people." "It nurtured the youthful vigor of those with a patriotic spirit." It produced a succession of international art masters, iconic figures in revolutionary art, leaders in higher education art disciplines, and pioneers in preserving Dunhuang art. The masters and renowned figures who emerged from the flames of the Second Sino-Japanese War during the National Academy of Art's legendary journey have left an indelible mark on modern art education in China. They serve as a banner institution of Chinese art education, exerting a profound influence on the development of modern art education in China and the progress of Chinese society.

3. Well-structured Teaching Activities

During this period, the school found itself in constant relocation and upheaval due to the turmoil of war. However, for these young students from all corners of the country and far from their hometowns, Anjiang Village was a rare “holy land” for artistic learning. During this time, the school further improved its *Code of Conduct*, which provided clear regulations for student enrollment, registration, fees, transfers, courses, examinations, promotion and retention, graduation, withdrawals, disciplinary actions, leaves of absence, and resumptions of studies.

The school’s curriculum was divided into two main categories: general courses and specialized courses. Available courses, including art history, art theory, and foreign languages, were open to all students. Specialized courses were organized into different groups, each with its curriculum. Within each group, specialized courses were further divided into fundamental theoretical courses and introductory creative courses.

The Chinese and Western painting figure classes during the Anjiang Village period left a profound impression on the students.

Chinese Painting Classes: The Chinese painting program at the National Academy of Art was established independently in its first year. Therefore, its curriculum and teaching methods were an exploratory journey during this period. The Chinese painting group, led by Pan Tianshou, offered foundational courses like Chinese Painting Theory and Introduction to Chinese Painting. It integrated introductory training courses such as painting, colour theory, and sketching throughout the curriculum. They followed the traditional Chinese painting education model, which includes poetry, calligraphy, and artwork, offering courses like Poetry Selection,⁸ Lyric Selection, Calligraphy, and Inscription.

Pan Tianshou told his students: “We are powerless to save the nation, but we can, like Rabindranath Tagore, save our country through culture. You are still young; you must work hard to study our national culture, striving to reach new heights. By developing generation after generation, even if China falls, our national culture will continue.” From these words, it is evident that Pan Tianshou always held a deep determination and courage to revive Chinese culture through art, and he had a strong sense of reaching artistic peaks. He demanded excellence in himself, his students, and the field of education, persistently expressing his faith in the importance of national culture.

Among them, the painting course, which served as a foundation-building exercise, had the most class hours.

The painting class was essentially about the practice of copying or imitation. National Academy of Art instructors for Chinese painting, including Pan Tianshou, primarily taught by imitating excellent works by ancient artists, explaining fundamental painting principles and techniques while encouraging students to learn traditional painting methods. He believed that during the learning stage, students should earnestly and diligently put in the effort to imitate traditional works and should not try to take shortcuts or rely on clever tricks.⁹

The Chinese painting group also emphasized character development. Pan Tianshou believed that the quality of an artist’s work and their character were closely connected and inseparable. He stated, “In painting, one must possess talent, skill, knowledge, and virtue, and these four aspects must be in harmony, without one being greater. Virtue is the determining factor. Only with a high moral character can one produce high-quality art. To achieve this, one must relinquish the desire for fame and fortune. When these do not bind a person’s nature, they can express the true essence of beauty in art.” He also proposed, “It’s not easy to conquer a work of art.” 1940 Pan Tianshou wrote in the inscription for the 3rd National Academy of Art commemorative book, “A work of art must be able to represent a nation, an era, a region, and oneself to be considered qualified.”¹⁰ This reflects Pan Tianshou’s unwavering creative thought and pursuit. In the dark times of the old society, where the nation was weak, and the people were poor, the revitalization of national art became the main driving force behind Pan Tianshou’s artistic creation. This is why he dared to resist and put forth the essence of conquering in art.

Body painting classes: Despite being in a remote rural area with deep-seated feudal traditions, the Western painting group continued to offer figure drawing courses as part of their curriculum. At the time, the biggest challenge was finding nude models. Teachers had to search the village and persuade local men and women to pose as nude models. Wu Guanzhong, in his article *Anjiang Village*, recalled “You should know that the classroom was set up in a big temple. We painted naked men and women in front of the Bodhisattva. The situation was both awkward and severe. Ultimately, the school had to use wooden boards and curtains to hide the Bodhisattva. While modernists might find common ground with Picasso and the city’s temples, we were not willing to give up the fundamental skill of realistic nude painting. Anjiang Village’s temples were turned into Montmartre in Paris, while Kunming was still living under the threat of Japanese air raids. It was a special era, a special environment, and a special mindset.”¹¹

The students and temple deities lived and slept toge-

ther, embarking on their unique “spiritual journey” within China’s traditional Confucian and Daoist culture. Even in the face of challenging living conditions, the students’ enthusiasm for learning remained high. Wu Guanzhong recounted, “Despite the deplorable material living conditions and teaching facilities, the spirits of teachers and students were as high as ever. Their firm belief was that after the victory in the war, more talents would be needed to build the nation! The students, young men and women, were lively and energetic. In the classrooms, they copied the works of painters like Shi Tao, Bada Shanren, Shi Xie, and Qingteng, and they painted naked men and women in front of the deity statues. In ancient temples, they brought forth a different style from the flower lanterns echoing here for thousands of years. They painted landscapes and cottages, sang songs, and painted peasants making soy sauce and drinking tea...”

Although Anjiang Village was quite distant from the city, the teachers and students did not view it as a secluded paradise. They remained focused on their studies and maintained their connection with the outside world. Their hearts were still tied to the battlefield. With united efforts, they faced the challenging times together. Despite the harsh conditions for running the school, the National Academy of Art faculty and students did not forget to spread the cultural flame. They used education and culture to save the nation from peril.

In February and March 1940, the National Academy of Art organized a preparatory exhibition for the upcoming Chongqing Spring Labor Army Art Exhibition at the Yuhuang Pavilion on the Anjiang Village campus. Subsequently, over a hundred works were selected and sent to Chongqing for the Labor Army Art Exhibition on April 5, 1940. The proceeds from this exhibition supported the frontline of the war effort.

4. Interpretation and Artistic Spirit Embodied in the School Motto “Bo-Yue-Hong-Yi”

Anjiang Village once bore witness to a generation of artists and scholars who exemplified the virtues of Bo-Yue-Hong-Yi. The renowned masters who emerged from the National Academy of Art fondly remember their time spent in Anjiang Village. The school motto Bo-Yue-Hong-Yi is derived from the *Analects of Confucius*. Confucius said, “Learn extensively and hold on to propriety.” Zengzi said, “A scholar, in what way should he not be expansive and unwavering?” The report by Yan is commented on as follows: “Expansive in greatness and unwavering in determination. A scholar

should be expansive and unwavering. Only then can he shoulder heavy responsibilities and travel far.” Liu’s commentary says, “A scholar’s ambition, due to the importance of his responsibilities, must emphasize expansiveness, and due to the length of the path he must take, must emphasize determination.” The teachings of great philosophers and the wisdom of past sages make the moral significance clear. As people establish themselves and shape their actions, they should cherish learning widely and acting conscientiously. They aim to be expansive and unwavering. We hope that all students put this into practice in their lives.

The meaning of Bo-Yue extends to the domains of knowledge and the arts. Zhang Xuecheng stated, “Learning should be broad and disciplined. There has never been anyone who is disciplined without being broad in learning. Being broad but not scattered, and being disciplined without omissions, this is the path to cultivating profound knowledge.” Broadness is the stage for discipline, so discipline is founded upon breadth, and discipline is the refinement of breadth. The Tang Dynasty’s biography of Pei Xingjian reads, “Scholars who aspire to great achievements start with knowledge of things and later develop literary and artistic skills.” In the past, people often regarded knowledge of things as fundamental and literary and artistic skills as secondary. However, this is probably not accurate. Knowledge of things provides resources and experiences, so one should be broad. Literary and artistic skills achieve refinement and beauty, so one should be disciplined. In this context, Bo-Yue is nothing more than the spirit of synthesis and the modern spirit of science. When applied to scholarship, this spirit leads to the discovery of knowledge; when applied to literature and the arts, it leads to creativity.

The National Academy of Art strictly adhered to the school motto, and amid the sounds of artillery fire, they maintained their sincere determination to continue their artistic pursuits without faltering. On the one hand, the National Academy of Art faculty and students engaged in grassroots propaganda for the war effort during their free time, aiming to enlighten and educate the people. On the other hand, despite the extreme hardships faced during their relocations and the challenges of maintaining their studies, the National Academy of Art students did not let their pursuit of knowledge be hindered. They were actively involved in wartime propaganda and organized night schools for the local population, leaving a solid impact with a heightened sense of national pride wherever the college was situated.

At that time, Anjiang Village selflessly hosted and

Figures 3, 4. The former site of Anjiang Village (left) and the National Academy of Art before renovation (right).

nurtured the National Academy of Art faculty and students, providing them a temporary sanctuary in Kunming, where they gradually took root. These roots absorbed the essence of the local culture while being entwined with the emotions of the college's faculty and students. Collectively, they provided steadfast strength for the tree of Yunnan's art education. The college faculty and students, unwilling to succumb to despair and defeat in the face of the war, used their artistry to express an indomitable spirit of resistance. Through culture, they sought the path to national salvation. The Chinese nation has always had a profound connection to its roots. Like a river and its source or a tree and its roots, the source is essential for the flow, and the roots are vital for the branches. The origins are of utmost importance for the Chinese nation, connecting the past and the future. Finding these roots means rediscovering history, ensuring the perpetuation of education, and preserving the ancient heritage of Chinese civilization.

The passage of time has witnessed many changes, like the shifting sands of the sea. Over eighty years later, the National Academy of Art continues to pass on its legacy, illuminating the path for future generations. On June 29, 2023, participants of the National Art Fund's 2023 Talent Development Program for *Contemporary Art Design Review and Research* revisited Anjiang Village, where they explored the historic site of the National Academy of Art and experienced the essence of artistic education, known as the "Kuige Spirit".

The historic site of the National Academy of Art is still undergoing restoration, with exposed pipelines and remnants from the past scattered around. Despite the casual placement of information boards on the ground, the term "Spirit" on these boards stands out prominently. This term originates from the artistic and educational philosophy of Cai Yuanpei, the founder of the National Art College (formerly known as the National Academy of Art), enriched later by President Lin Fengmian. It evolved

into an ethos characterized by academic freedom and an all-encompassing learning culture.

From a holistic perspective, the old campus layout exhibits axial symmetry, aligning with the Confucian concept of *Zhong Yong* or The Doctrine of the Mean. The stone base supporting the wooden pillars of the attic is inscribed with the words “Built by the Public of Anjiang Village, Spring of the 36th Year of the Republic of China”. The earliest inscriptions on stones date back to the Qing Dynasty. The National Academy of Art’s settlement in Anjiang Village resembles a meeting of Confucian, Buddhist, and Daoist traditions. Anjiang is known for the saying, “Nine temples and two drum towers surround Anjiang”.

After they arrived in Anjiang, the National Academy of Art initially used temples like the Guanyin Temple, Great Buddha Temple, Dragon King Temple, Houji Temple, Dizang Temple, Guangong Temple, and Yuhuang Pavilion as their campuses. Students found

themselves living and studying within these temples, embarking on a unique spiritual journey in the context of traditional Chinese culture. They pursued the colleges’ educational philosophy: “Skills can lead to the Dao, Art can connect with the Divine”, implying that mastering the basics of a skill is the initial step, and further refinement and spiritual development will ultimately connect one to the realm of the Dao, a level of understanding the laws of the universe.

We visited the restoration site of Yuhuang Pavilion and then researched the historical documents and materials related to the National Academy of Art. This allowed us to deeply appreciate the historical significance and value of Anjiang Village in the context of Chinese art education. We were not only inspired by the artistry and educational philosophy of these masters but also realized the importance and urgency of continuing their legacy in contemporary university art education and creative research.

Figure 5. The former site of Anjiang Village, National Academy of Art, before renovation.

The old site of the National Academy of Art in Anjiang Village carries the patriotic sentiments of the National Academy of Art's faculty and students, who were committed to the rise and fall of the nation. It bears the spirit of patriotism, resilience, and dedication, testifying to the efforts made by the National Academy of Art's faculty and students to protect China's 5,000 years of civilization and continue the cultural and artistic heritage of the Chinese nation. It is a precious spiritual treasure that serves as a reminder to commemorate the great victory of the Second Sino-Japanese War, promote the spirit of the war, carry out patriotic education, and foster art creation and art education, which is of great significance.

The strings' unbroken melodies and the torch's passing on have been the fundamental forces that enabled the National Academy of Art to overcome all challenges during wartime. The robust national spirit and unwavering determination in education supported the Nation-

al Academy of Art faculty and students as they strove for self-improvement amid turbulence, persevered through wandering, and navigated crises. They composed an educational marvel where the National Academy of Art continued to thrive despite the environment of "endangered culture and extinction".

The roots of the National Academy of Art have long been embedded in the soil of local culture and the arts, silently influencing Yunnan throughout history. As the saying goes, "A towering tree must have its roots; water that nurtures the mountain must have its source." History is the source of the present, and it subtly permeates the bloodstream of art education, forming an indispensable foundation for future development.

On January 20, 2020, during his inspection visit to the old site of Southwest Associated University, General Secretary Xi Jinping emphasized the connection between education and the nation's destiny, particularly during times of national crisis. He remarked that during the

nation's most challenging moments, the essence of our education was gathered and refined here, creating a situation where elites congregated. Eventually, this is where these talents bore fruit. They also spread their knowledge to make valuable contributions to various historical periods of revolution, construction, and reform. This profoundly reminds us that education must be closely linked to the country's fate and the nation's future. Working for the country and the nation is the driving force and motivation for learning. Harsh and straightforward conditions can indeed be the birthplace of great talents. The purpose of education today is to nurture builders and successors of socialism, to cultivate new individuals of the era with a sense of history, responsibility, and lofty aspirations, and not to disappoint the times.

Currently, China finds itself in a transformative era that occurs once in a century, and education bears the mission of strengthening the nation, taking on the responsibility of promoting the country's rise. At this critical juncture in history, revisiting Anjiang Village and recalling the spirit and traditions of the faculty and students of the National Academy of Art during wartime, who endured extraordinary hardships and embraced the spirit of broad learning and firm determination, remains relevant today as we move forward with the times.

Over the past century of modern education development in China, we have often been accustomed to "seeking from afar" and constantly looking outward for inspiration and innovation. However, we may have forgotten to look within ourselves and acknowledge the excellent traditions and successful experiences already present in our own country. The experiences of other countries may not necessarily fit the soil of China, so

when searching for treasures from other lands, we should never forget to draw wisdom and nourishment from our history. Only then can we make choices more tailored to China's unique characteristics and aligned with its practical needs, paving the way for a Chinese-style modernization.

Innovating or perishing doesn't mean breaking free from history and reality. What we consider old history may very well provide the most suitable answers to today's challenges. History may not speak, but it bears witness to everything. In the face of a national crisis, the choices of many individuals ultimately form a nation's options. Over eighty years ago, to preserve the nation's vitality, the faculty and students of the National Academy of Art embarked on a migration journey without hesitation. They endured hardships, yet their original intentions remained unwavering. Throughout the difficult years of war, they held fast to their principles and missions, and the ordinary people who welcomed them in their new homes generously shared their resources. Together, they echoed the same aspirations and disseminated the national pulse of the country and the academic pulse of the National Academy of Art. A university's glory, pride, responsibilities, and missions shone brightly in that generation of scholars.

Today, this chapter of history may be receding into the past, but it is far from leaving no trace. The sparks of thought and the strength of spirit will continue to be reborn in a new era. With their enduring vitality, they will be embedded in the spiritual fabric of the Chinese people, shaping cultural heritage and passing the torch, remaining ever fresh.

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重返安江村——國立藝專的思想文脈及藝術教育理念

姚風

摘要：1939年北平藝專和杭州藝專合並成立的國立藝專西遷至安江村，開啟了一段短暫卻至為關鍵的辦學時光。眾多師生積極投身文藝戰線，勳力同心，共克時艱，即使辦學條件艱苦，藝專師生在烽火中仍不忘傳播文化火種，以教育文化挽救民族於危亡間。創作了大量優秀作品，培養了眾多傑出的藝術家，在中國現代美術史上寫下了光輝的一頁，同時也為新中國文藝、文化、文教美育和宣傳事業的發展儲備了大量人才，對我國藝術教育事業產生了深遠的影響。

關鍵詞：安江村；國立藝專；抗戰救國；思想文脈；藝術教育